

Homeopathy in veterinary medicine

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Received: 21.04.2025

Accepted: 01.05.2025

Published: 02.05.2025

Abstract

Homeopathy, a natural treatment that provides the body to heal itself and has no significant side effects, is one of the complementary and alternative treatment methods in both human and animal health. From past to present, many cultures have developed different treatment methods using natural resources, and traditional treatment systems have had an important place among these methods that have survived until today. Homeopathy was first applied and developed in Germany by Dr. Samuel Hahnemann (1755-1843). The basis of the treatment method, which is a holistic approach, is based on the principle of “similia similibus curentur”, that is, “like cures like”. The first homeopathic treatment in animals was tried by Baron von Boenninghausen in 1785. Homeopathy contributes to animal health and welfare by providing benefits in the prevention and treatment of diseases. Homeopathic treatment in veterinary medicine is widely used in our country and in the world in order to increase the chance of success in treatment. Although this type of treatment is controversial from an academic medical perspective, evidence-based research supporting its effectiveness has increased in recent years. As a result, we believe that additional studies are needed in addition to the studies in this area.

Keywords: *Alternative therapy, homeopathy, medicine, veterinary*

1. INTRODUCTION

Homeopathy is one of the most common treatment methods used in alternative medicine today.¹ The word homeopathy is of Greek origin and means “similar” (ómoio) and “pain” (páthi).² The basic law of this holistic treatment method, developed and frequently used by the German physician Samuel Hahnemann, is “similia similibus curentur”, meaning “like cures like”.³ In 1785, Baron von Boenninghausen first used homeopathy on animals.^{4,5} The entire life story of the sick animal from the day it was born until it came to the clinic, detailed anamnesis and mental, physical and spiritual changes are examined and the patient is considered as a whole.⁶ The aim of homeopathy is to contribute to the recovery of the sick animal and to maintain and make this quality of life permanent throughout its life. It shapes this recovery process by loading the energy needed by the sick animal into its body and starting the body to heal itself.⁷ The substances found in nature and to be used for homeopathy are called remedies and are subjected to a series of processes called potentization or strengthening for their preparation. With potentization, the inert main substance is diluted and the energy of the substance is released. Thus, the healing energy needed by the body is met and the healing process begins.⁸ The choice of remedy is completely patient-specific and is not chosen based on symptoms as in traditional medicine. For the selection of remedy, help is obtained from *Materia medica*, where the data is recorded.⁹

In veterinary medicine, homeopathy is used both for

therapeutic and preventive purposes in a wide range of conditions, including acute or chronic inflammation, trauma, injuries, behavioral disorders, allergies, infertility, side effects following vaccination, parasitic diseases, tumoral formations, metabolic disorders, and endocrine diseases.^{10,11} When choosing the medicine to be used in homeopathy, it is important that the veterinarian is competent in the fields of homeopathy, physiology and pathology, that the medicine chosen is not for the disease but for the patient and the patient’s individual characteristics and habits, and in this context, a detailed information obtained from the patient’s owner is important. Otherwise, wrong medicine selection and dosage applications made by people who do not receive sufficient training lead to side effects and therefore to the failure of the treatment.^{12,13}

2. HISTORY OF HOMEOPATHY

Homeopathy has existed in various forms since ancient times. There are references to the use of homeopathic principles in the records of the ancient Egyptians, Chinese, Incas, Aztecs, and Native Americans.^{14,15} Various practices based on homeopathic principles have been described over the centuries, but homeopathy was not systematically organized and practiced until the late 1800s, when Dr. Samuel Hahnemann, a German physician, developed the science of homeopathy. The fundamental concept of homeopathy, the “principle of similars,” was described and used by Hippocrates.¹⁵ Hahnemann believed that a disease could be cured by

giving a drug that would produce similar symptoms of the same disease, but in a milder degree, when given to a healthy person. He noted that regular doses of cinchona (quinine) produced all the symptoms of malaria, but in a milder degree and without the characteristic symptoms. This led Hahnemann to an idea published in 1796 as *Essay on a New Principle for Ascertaining the Curative Power of Drugs*, and in 1810 he published his famous work *The Organon of the Healing Art*.¹⁶ Because homeopathy was based on such opposing principles, homeopaths received negative criticism from allopathic and conventional practitioners. Despite this, homeopathy was well known in Europe and America, and its use increased in India in the early 1900s. However, during the 1900s, the practice of homeopathy gradually disappeared in North America, partly because of the increasing interest in technological advances, partly because of the continuing opposition of allopathic practitioners and associations, and because of selective approaches that departed from Dr. Hahnemann's classical approach and were not effective in carrying out therapies. In Europe, however, homeopathy remained an established method of treatment. The Royal Hospital for Homeopathy in London continued its activities, and in India, homeopathy flourished, partly because of the low cost of homeopathic medicines and the lack of expensive technology.¹⁵

3. PRINCIPLES OF HOMEOPATHY

3.1. Law of Similars (*Similia Similibus Curantur*)

According to homeopathic philosophy, the symptoms that occur during an illness are considered to be reactions that help the body adapt to factors such as infectious agents and stress. In this context, a substance that will cause similar symptoms when given in high doses may trigger the body's defense mechanism when given in very small amounts.¹⁵ Following this concept, homeopathy focuses on strengthening the patient's life force by triggering similar symptoms rather than trying to eliminate symptoms. In essence, homeopathy is a treatment system based on the principle of '*Similia similibus curantur*', meaning 'like cures like'.¹⁷ In the disease to be cured, especially if it is chronic, the drug that is likely to induce another artificially produced disease in a similar way as possible should be applied, and the first will be cured - *similia similibus* - like with like. That is, to cure the disease, we must seek drugs that can induce similar symptoms in the healthy human body.¹⁷

3.2. Life Force Theory

According to the life force theory, for any treatment to be effective, the body's response must be adequate. Each individual has a life energy, defined as a vital force, that serves as the true healing force. In homeopathy, the application of a similar remedy aims to stimulate this vital force and facilitate healing.¹⁸

3.3. Single Drug and Minimum Effective Dose Principle

Classical homeopathy, developed by Hahnemann, is based on the practice of using a single drug that matches the patient's symptoms and disease presentation without mixing different drugs. Studies evaluating the effectiveness of homeopathic remedies are also conducted

with a single drug. This approach is necessary because only one drug should closely match the patient's condition. When more than one drug is used, it becomes unclear which drug is responsible for the observed effects. Using more than one drug can lead to interactions that increase or eliminate each other's effects.⁸ In addition to the principle of using a single remedy, another critical factor affecting the success of homeopathic treatment is the principle of the minimum effective dose. According to this principle, the specific therapeutic effects of a remedy tend to occur when the smallest but most effective dose is administered. Administration of high doses may affect the vital force beyond the capacity to perceive, potentially resulting in treatment failure.¹⁸

4. USE OF HOMEOPATHY IN VETERINARY MEDICINE

Homeopathy applications have been used in animal health for many years, both preventively and curatively.¹⁹ It has begun to be preferred by both veterinarians and patient owners in terms of animal welfare because it shortens the treatment period, uses a natural drug compared to traditional medicine, and therefore does not contain antibacterial drug residues in meat and milk in organic livestock farming, and does not cause immunosuppression or local abscesses or nodules after application.^{8,12} It is used to treat and take preventive measures for many conditions such as acute or chronic inflammation, trauma, injury, behavioral disorders, allergy, infertility, side effects after vaccination, parasitic diseases, tumoral formations, metabolic disorders and endocrine diseases seen in small animals and large cattle.^{6,20-22} When choosing the drug to be used in homeopathy, it is important that the veterinarian is competent in the fields of homeopathy, physiology and pathology, the drug selected is not for the disease but for the patient and the patient's individual characteristics and habits, and in this context, a detailed information obtained from the patient's owner is important. Otherwise, wrong drug selection and dosage applications made by people who do not receive sufficient training lead to side effects and therefore to the failure of the treatment.^{6,23}

In veterinary homeopathy, there are many remedies used depending on the cases. Nosodes act as immune modulators. Distemper, Kennel cough, feline flu, feline AIDS, feline leukemia are the main pet diseases that are helped by nosodes.^{1,24} Homeopathic materials are used in different fields in humans and animals, and their indications are given in Table 1.

5. CONCLUSION

As a result, different diseases are constantly emerging in medical science. Although medical science is generally developing, some deficiencies in treatments are revealed and there may be delays in treatment. Therefore, alternative treatment methods are of great importance. Therefore, researching alternative treatments such as homeopathy is very important. Scientific studies to be conducted in this field will be more effective in treating diseases. Since medicine is a whole, joint studies will be important without making any distinction between veterinary medicine and human medicine. We believe that the importance of homeopathy and similar alternative treatments will become even more important in the future.

Table 1. Some homeopathic materials used in veterinary medicine and indications.^{1,10,13,8,25,26}

MATERIAL NAME	INDICATION
Aconite (<i>Aconitum napellus</i>)	Asthma, incoordination, shock, viral and bacterial inflammation, coccidiosis, encephalitis, Escherichia coli (E. coli) infection, omphalophlebitis, toxoplasmosis
Aloe vera (<i>Aloe vera</i>)	Mastitis
Antimony Arsenic (<i>Antimonium arsenicum</i>)	Pulmonary edema and emphysema
Antimony Crude (<i>Antimonium crudum</i>)	Tympany
Arborvitae (<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>)	Asthma, diuretics, pseudopregnancy in dogs
Arsenic Album (<i>Arsenicum album</i>)	Allergy, flea infestation, asthma
Barberry (<i>Berberis vulgaris</i>)	Acute nephritis
Bearberry (<i>Uva ursi</i>)	Acute nephritis
Belladonna (<i>Atropa belladonna</i>)	CNS disorders, abscess, encephalitis
Benzoic Acid (<i>Benzoicum acidum</i>)	Omphalophlebitis, pyelonephritis
Beryllium (<i>Beryllium</i>)	Pneumonia
Bushmaster Snake (<i>Lachesis muta</i>)	Allergy, colic, mastitis, genital diseases, flea infestations
Calcium Fluoride (<i>Calcarea fluorica</i>)	Pericarditis
Calcium Phosphate (<i>Calcarea phosphorica</i>)	Osteodystrophy, Calcium-phosphorus deficiency
Chamomile (<i>Chamomilla</i>)	Inflammation and pain during teething in young puppies
Chaste Tree (<i>Agnus castus</i>)	Disorders of the estrous cycle in dogs
Cinchona (Quinine) (<i>China officinalis</i>)	Babesiosis, anaplasmosis
Clubmoss (<i>Lycopodium</i>)	Gastritis, anorexia, allergy, flea infestations
Cobra Venom (<i>Naja tripudians</i>)	Endocarditis
Colocynth (<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i>)	Colic
Comfrey (<i>Symphytum</i>)	Rapid healing of bone damage
Common Toad (<i>Bufo rana</i>)	CNS disorders, paralysis, motor disturbances associated with viral infections
Cuban Tarantula (<i>Tarantula cubensis</i>)	Reduction of vaginal discharge intensity, acceleration of uterine involution, prevention of retained placenta, prevention of tumor formation
Cuttlefish Ink (<i>Sepia</i>)	Sexual cycle disorders in cows, hepatitis, hepatic insufficiency, management of behavioral issues in dogs that do not care for their puppies or eat their young
Echinacea (<i>Echinacea angustifolia</i>)	Inflammation, metritis, immunomodulators
Eyebright (<i>Euphrasia</i>)	Allergy, corneal ulcer, conjunctivitis
Graphite (<i>Graphites</i>)	Colic
Hawthorn (<i>Crataegus</i>)	Myocarditis
Hekla Lava (<i>Hekla lava</i>)	Actinomycosis-Actinobacillosis
Hepar Sulphur (<i>Hepar sulphuris</i>)	Septic and purulent infections
Honeybee (<i>Apis mellifica, Apis</i>)	Arthritis, mastitis, edema, infertility
Ipecac (<i>Ipeca</i>)	Colic, diarrhea, asthma, allergic reactions
Jimson Weed (<i>Stramonium</i>)	Ketosis, encephalitis, magnesium deficiency
Magnesium Phosphate (<i>Magnesium phosphoricu</i>)	Magnesium deficiency
Marigold (<i>Calendula</i>)	Wound healing, coccidiosis
Marsh Ledum (<i>Ledum palustre</i>)	Allergy, flea infestations
Mistletoe (<i>Viscum album</i>)	Tumoral formations
Nettle (<i>Urtica</i>)	Urticaria, milk production inhibition in mammary glands
Night-Blooming Cereus(<i>Cactus crandiflorus</i>)	Endocarditis
Nutmeg (<i>Nux mochata</i>)	Asthma
Phosphate of Iron (<i>Ferrum phosphoricum</i>)	Anorexia
Phosphorus (<i>Phosphorus</i>)	Babesiosis, anaplasmosis, toxoplasmosis, anemia, diarrhea
Poison Ivy (<i>Rhus toxicodendron</i>)	Rheumatism, arthritis, allergy
Poke Root (<i>Phytolacca decondra</i>)	Mammary gland hardness, pain and edema
Pokeweed (<i>Phytolacca americana</i>)	Anaplasmosis

Table 1: Continued

MATERIAL NAME	INDICATION
Potassium Arsenic (<i>Kali Arsenicum</i>)	Scabies, nematodes
Potassium Bichromate (<i>Kali Bichromium</i>)	Colic
Potassium Iodide (<i>Kali Hydriodicum</i>)	Actinomycosis-Actinobacillosis
Psora (<i>Psorinum</i>)	Scabies, anemia
Rue (<i>Ruta</i>)	Conditions affecting ligaments, tendons, and other fibrous tissues
Sacred Fig (<i>Ficus religiosa</i>)	Babesiosis
Savin (<i>Sabina</i>)	Puerperal metritis
Senna (<i>Cassia sophera</i>)	Asthma
Silica (<i>Silicea</i>)	Necrotic hepatitis, hepatic abscess, pyelonephritis
Sodium Chloride (Common Salt) (<i>Natrum muriaticum</i>)	Fungal infections, anemia, canine atopic dermatitis
Spanish Fly (<i>Cantharis</i>)	Peritonitis
St. John's Wort (<i>Hypericum</i>)	Pain, wounds, coccidiosis, tetanus
Stinging Nettle (<i>Urtica urens</i>)	Asthma, allergic reactions
Strychnine Tree (<i>Nux vomica</i>)	Intoxication, constipation, intervertebral disc disease in dogs, laminitis, stress, colic, anorexia, gastritis, tetanus, ketosis
Tellurium (<i>Tellurium</i>)	Nematodes
Thyroid Gland (<i>Thyroidinum</i>)	Asthma
TNT (explosive) (<i>Trinitrotoluene</i>)	Anaplasmosis, anemia
Tuberculin (<i>Tuberculinum</i>)	Asthma
Vegetable Charcoal (<i>Carbo vegetabilis</i>)	Tympany, Escherichia coli, mastitis
White Bryony (<i>Bryonia alba</i>)	Mammary gland hardness, pain and edema, arthritis, pneumonia
White Hellebore (<i>Veratrum album</i>)	Coccidiosis
Windflower (<i>Pulsatilla miniplex</i>)	Gastritis, aggression, infertility, uterine contractions
Witch Hazel (<i>Hamamelis</i>)	Hemorrhagic and fistulous wounds
Yarrow (<i>Millefolium</i>)	Babesiosis

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